

Recommended citation: Zaneldin, E., Shekfa, M. I., Hilal-Alnaqbi, A., & Ahmed, W. K. (2017). Teaching Engineering Economy Using Internet . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 803-810). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698263.

Teaching Engineering Economy Using Internet

Essam Zaneldin

Ph.D., Associate Professor
ERU & Civil Engineering Department, College of Engineering, UAE University
Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
E-mail: essamz@uaeu.ac.ae

Mohammed Ismaeel Shekfa

M.Sc., Lecturer
ERU, College of Engineering, UAE University
Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
E-mail: mshekfa@uaeu.ac.ae

Ali Hilal-Alnaqbi

Ph.D., Associate Professor
Mechanical Engineering Department, College of Engineering, UAE University
Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
E-mail: alihilal@uaeu.ac.ae

Waleed K Ahmed¹

Ph.D., Lecturer
ERU & Mechanical Engineering Department, College of Engineering, UAE University
Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
E-mail: w.ahmed@uaeu.ac.ae

ABSTRACT

Internet-based education is rapidly gaining popularity due to its availability, flexibility, accessibility, and cost effectiveness. In this research, the internet was used as an effective tool to enhance the teaching of the “Engineering Economy” course GENG315 at the foundation level in the college at a federal university in UAE. It is noticed that numerous related course material is available online as “YouTube” videos. Therefore, a carefully selected material was nominated and distributed to students during the course. A questionnaire survey was then conducted to analyze the impact of the experiment that reflects the positive aspects of video-based learning.

Conference Key Areas: Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning, Open and Online Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Engineering Economy, Internet, YouTube, Active Learning

¹ Corresponding Author
Waleed K Ahmed
w.ahmed@uaeu.ac.ae

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the internet becomes widely used all over the world without any boundaries and limitations of the uses and applications. Actually, this imposes many advantages and disadvantages on the life in general and on the education in particular. However, one of the main advantages of the internet is deploying the knowledge everywhere without any restrictions. Using videos in teaching becomes recently a trend around the world to enhance the learning pedagogy and students outcomes attainments. Meanwhile nowadays with the rapid development of the communication and social media technologies, the students they become more distracted by the internet itself. Therefore adopting the E-Learning in teaching would be simulative factor to the students in all levels [1-3]. Moreover, the internet technology can be helpful and positive as a tool to diminish the negative impact of the internet like the social media, since the students may spend hours in browsing news and neglecting their academic duties. YouTube, for example, became one of easy and free sources that can be accessed easily and can be used to upload videos that can be watched around the world. This channel has been used tremendously in teaching to enhance the learning experience and to keep permanently the material as an open resource for the students to study or to refresh their memories. Frongia et al. [4] analyzed the surgical proficiency and educational quality of YouTube videos demonstrating laparoscopic fundoplication (LF). A search was performed on YouTube for videos demonstrating the LF procedure. The surgical and educational proficiency was evaluated using the objective component rating scale, the educational quality rating score, and total video quality score. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) of YouTube was studied by Chintalapati et al. [5], by developing scales to measure the factors explaining the behavioral intention and established the significance of the relationship between different variables and the behavioral intention validating the TAM. In the medical field, YouTube has its advantages in many ways. Duncan et al. [6] described the findings of a study undertaken to assess the quality of clinical skills videos available on the video sharing site YouTube by evaluating 100 YouTube sites, approximately 1500 min or 25 h worth of content across 10 common clinical skill-related topics. It was concluded that there is a clear need for the quality of YouTube videos to be subjected to a rigorous evaluation. Besides, it is recommended that lecturers should be more proactive in recommending suitable YouTube material as supplementary learning materials after appropriately checking for quality. On the other hand, YouTube offers visual access to childhood illnesses and disease processes to the medical students may not encounter during their regular pediatric clinical rotations. Videos from hospitals, healthcare organizations, news media, and personal accounts are all available to enhance and stimulate the learning process [7]. Moreover, YouTube offers nurse educators immediate access to healthcare related videos for the classroom. In classrooms that are equipped with Internet and projectors, educators can quickly access YouTube and utilize videos to meet classroom objectives, as explained by Agazio and Buckley [8]. In addition, Rapp et al. [9] discovered that the most widely used video source used in preparation for surgical procedures is YouTube. The relatively recent increase in video availability and use presents an opportunity to create new training tools for students, residents, and faculty in the surgical field, not as a replacement, but as an addition to established teaching methods. De Witt et.al. [10], studied the benefits of the use of YouTube as a tool for teaching and learning in the performing arts, and for maintaining students' interest and achievement in learning, as well as to determine the suitability of using YouTube as a tool for teaching the performing arts in future. The findings show the YouTube has the potential as an instructional tool in the performing arts in line with current trends of collaboration and social networking in education. YouTube videos were selected to enhance course topics and materials found in traditional text-based

materials. Original videos were created in the style of Khan Academy, to prerecord short lectures promote in the literature on case teaching and flip format learning. Online course evaluations measured student progress on learning objectives [11]. In the present study, YouTube has been used to enhance the learning experience of the students in the foundation level of the college of engineering. Engineering economy course GENG 305 was selected for this purpose to investigate the effectiveness of the YouTube in enhancing the students' performance in the course.

1 METHODOLOGY

In order to improve the students' understanding of the topics of the "Engineering Economy" course GENG315 in the college of engineering at UAEU, a pre-assessment was performed to figure out the topics that are considered as weak points for the students understanding. Therefore, a careful list of suggested videos from the YouTube was selected to perform the main goal of the task. *Table 1* illustrates the nominated subjects that were delivered to the students. When the targeted subjects were completely covered, the suggested topics were delivered to 40 students one week before the midterm, and later on the feedbacks were collected after the exam.

Table 1. The suggested videos for engineering economy course

	YouTube links	Subjects
1	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zGRVVSC4UUQ	Evaluating investment by PW
2	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fM63moi1Qjo	Time value of money
3	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q299WQqSGFo	Annuity
4	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n4QINzCCKGE	time value of money
5	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5IUqITdBF2M	Types of Interest
6	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VaZLXTULXqE	Present Worth - Fundamentals of Engineering Economics
7	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ILuKPh8WM6w	compound interest
8	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GeHu6YoG9B0	Present Worth
9	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SNoPFiFHkBA	Present and Future Value
10	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B3ldfBcXrLA&list=TLBq2QmPod-nQBJeVkrRq0JdQlabXL23iIS	Simple and Compound Interest
11	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=joBu9TnFngQ	Annuities: Annuity Due, Finding Future Value
12	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cVXYiWRZd7U	Compound Interest: Present Value/Future Value
13	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CnRJ6Jypsj4	Time Value of Money
14	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lonXkP0gl7o	Engineering Economics
15	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2nYkCfdiC3E	Future Worth - Fundamentals of Engineering Economics
16	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VyReAhTBvOw	Present value, future value, and compounding made easy
17	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FnzoTQMClO4	Future Value of Money Calculation -Basic - tutorial video lesson review
18	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kega_QOCvxQ	Cash Flow - Fundamentals of Engineering Economics
19	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kwlWeijKUNo	New Car Buying vs. Leasing, Part 1
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FtAZD4R-Wh0	New Car Buying vs. Leasing, Part 2
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NmzEqkiF3Eo	New Car Buying vs. Leasing, Part 3
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=szIYT8uNJII	New Car Buying vs. Leasing, Part 4
20	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=69mVcnewPbw	Break Even Analysis

2 QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

A questionnaire survey was designed and conducted among students to explore their feedback regarding the distributed course material and its level of usefulness. Their feedback was then used to analyze the impact of this experience on students' understanding of the subject topics and their performance in the course. *Table 2* shows the questions of the survey. Students were asked to provide a score on a scale from "1 to 5" for each question, where one represents "very low" agreement level and five is "very high" level of agreement.

Table 2. The distributed questionnaire survey

	Questions	Score:1-5
Q1	In general, do you prefer to study through videos	
Q2	Do you think that the videos selected were helpful	
Q3	Were the materials in general similar to the one you are studying	
Q4	Do you prefer your instructor to do videos	
Q5	Do you like presenter to be shown in the video	
Q6	Did you get helpful assistance from the watched videos	
Q7	Was the material of some videos distracting?	
Q8	Do you think that some videos contain materials not taking	
Q9	Is it better to have blended learning	
Q10	Are the videos clear enough to understand?	
Q11	Do you prefer to have videos on UAEU website rather than using YouTube	
Q12	Do you think videos are made for business purposes rather than education	
Q13	The main problem of the videos is the recording type	
Q14	Was the sound clear enough	
Q15	Good video material can help you to understand the subject	
Q16	Do you like to have videos of the presented lectures	
Q17	Do you like to have videos of extra solved cases	
Q18	Did you like to involve in this survey to improve teaching of the course	
Q19	Do you think that answering this survey will make change in this experience	
Q20	In general, do you think it is better for other courses to start using videos	

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Once the survey feedback was collected, the results were analyzed to investigate the impact on students' performance in studying the "Engineering Economy" course GENG315. Figure 1 shows the results of the responses (as a percentage) for the 20 questions considered in this study. In general, Q1 shows that 92.5% of the respondents showed their interest in studying through videos. On the other hand, 100% of students considered watching the videos is helpful to them, which is a positive sign, as illustrated by Q2 responses. In addition, 100% believe that the material selected coincided with the one they take in the course and this is an indication regarding the carefully selected videos that were nominated and reviewed based on the course subjects (i.e., Q3). However, frankly, they prefer that the course instructor records the videos and that the instructor photo to be shown in the prepared videos, both of them got 100%, this is revealed through Q4 and Q5 feedbacks.

Fig. 1. The results of the distributed survey

In general, question 6 is linked with question 2, and both questions show close feedback about the helpfulness of the watched videos. The results of questions 7 of the survey revealed that 47.5% of students believe that some videos are distracting and that urges to establish course videos by the instructors themselves. In response to question 8, around the same percentage indicated that some videos contain irrelevant material to the course. Around 57.5% like to have blended learning that needs more efforts to deploy it in general in order to attract more students, as revealed by question 9 feedbacks, whereas question 11 shows that the selected videos are clear technically. All respondents believe that the nominated videos are clear enough while the majority of respondents (85%) believe that instructors should have videos posted on the university website to make it easy for them to browse it (i.e., Q11). The responses to question 12 indicate that around 55% of the students believe that the videos published are for marketing and advertisement purposes. Two technical problems are highlighted in response to questions 13 and 14 that attracted 80% and 95% respectively that is the recording type of the videos as well as the quality of the sound that made the students unhappy with these issues. Question 15 shows that around 95% of the respondents are satisfied with the video' material for a better grasp to the course while they prefer that videos be prepared and recorded by the course instructor. As part of the learning experience, all students believe that solving more problems is very helpful for students to grasp better the course material, as well as to have videos of the presented lectures, as shown in Q16 and Q17. In addition, all students believe that this survey will improve the teaching and learning of the course (i.e., Q18). In response to question 19, around 95% of the respondents are optimistic to see changes based on this initiative. Eventually, all students indicated that other courses should similar steps since this is the new global trend nowadays, this is recommended by question 20 feedbacks. The data received from the questionnaire responses was carefully analyzed and the Relative Importance Index (RII) [12], was calculated as shown in *Table 3* to determine the relative importance of the responses to each question. The Relative Importance Index (RII) was calculated using following equation:

$$RII_k^i(\%) = (n_1 + 2n_2 + 3n_3 + 4n_4 + 5n_5)/(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + n_5) \times 100$$

where $RII_k^i(\%)$ is the Relative Importance Index of each factor i , for each group of students, k , while $n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4,$ and n_5 are the number of students who provided a score of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively.

Table 3, illustrates the ranks of the calculated RII for the responses of the 20 questionnaire survey questions. The ranking was grouped into three main categories (shown in Figure 2). In conclusion, around 40% of the respondents strongly believe that using videos through the study of the course is very useful and using extra videos will, undoubtedly, enhance the learning process. Students also believe that introducing videos in classes will have positive changes and implications to the learning process. Moreover, the helpfulness of watching the videos and the similarity between the materials watched and that studied in the course are positive as well.

Table 3. Relative Importance Index (RII) of the collected feedbacks

	Question number of students	Rank	RII
Q16	Do you like to have videos of the presented lectures	1	93
Q17	Do you like to have videos of extra solved cases	2	90
Q4	Do you prefer your instructor to do videos	2	90
Q18	Did you like to involve in this survey to improve teaching of the course	4	88
Q19	Do you think that answering this survey will make change in this experience	5	84
Q15	Good video material can help you to understand the subject	6	83
Q20	In general, do you think it is better for other courses to start videos	7	81
Q3	Were the materials in general similar to the one you are studying	7	81
Q11	Do you prefer to have videos on UAEU website rather than using YouTube	9	79
Q2	Do you think that the videos selected were helpful	10	77
Q5	Do you like presenter to be shown in the video	11	76
Q6	Did you get helpful assistance from the videos seen	12	75
Q14	Was the sound clear enough	12	75
Q1	In general, do you prefer to study through videos	14	74
Q10	Are the videos clear enough to understand?	15	71
Q13	The main problem of the videos is the recording type	16	65
Q9	Is it better to have blended learning	17	58
Q12	Do you think videos are made for business purposes rather than education	18	53
Q8	Do you think that some videos contain materials not taking	19	46
Q7	Was the material of some videos are distracting	20	45

Around 25% of the respondents expressed their opinions regarding the negative impression about using YouTube videos in the learning process. The main concern, in the opinion of respondents, is the type of videos, being used for advertisement purposes, not relating material well as some of them were distracting the students. In fact, the authors believe that students misunderstood question 9, which was ranked 17 with an RII of 58%, and assessed it wrongly. The response to this question was supposed to be positive since blended learning is expected to improve the learning pedagogy and, therefore, the responses to this question are considered irrelevant.

Fig. 2. Relative Importance Index: Percentage response

The medium range of the RII (71-79%) shown in Table 3 represents the 9 to 15 rank range. It is revealed that establishing videos by the university is important since videos are very helpful in the learning process. It is also preferred that instructors themselves record such videos to make sure that the quality is good and the sound and videos are clear. The top-ranked RII showed the significance impact of the watched videos with emphases on the importance of having videos for course lectures, especially for extra-solved problems related to course materials. Respondents also suggested that such videos should be recorded by course instructors. Questions 18 and 19 also provided positive students' feedback and the results depicted from the questionnaire survey responses suggest that the expected changes and improvements in the learning of the course are indeed an encouraging factor. Finally, it is worthwhile mentioning that the watched videos, related to the course material, were successfully selected for practicing and were very helpful for a better understanding of course material. Students, therefore, suggested following the same trend for the other courses.

4 SUMMARY

The present work shows the advantage of using the internet as a tool for learning purposes through using carefully selected videos to form YouTube channel. However, although there are some concerns from the students, but this survey highlights the need for building own learning videos for a better grasp. Further analysis is need after final exam results to compare the course outcomes of the course of the particularly investigated section, with results revealed by the present study to get a comprehensive image of the study advantages.

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